
European Journal of Studies in Management and Business

(Formerly *Management and Business Research Quarterly*)

<https://eurokd.com/journal/jd/16>

ISSN: 2667-6761

European Journal of Studies in Management and Business (Formerly Management and Business Research Quarterly) ISSN: **2667-6761** publishes articles reporting research in the field of management and business. The journal is an open-access and peer-reviewed quarterly journal to provide a platform for scientists and academicians all over the world to promote, share, and discuss various new issues and developments in different areas of business and management. The submissions should be in topics related to business and management effectiveness, and competitiveness including strategic management, management of marketing, AI in business, business management, business performance management, current approaches and challenges in management and business, and new trends in business and management.

Aim and Scope

European Journal of Studies in Management and Business (Formerly Management and Business Research Quarterly) is a peer-reviewed open access journal that publishes research in management and business. The journal is a venue for research that demonstrates robust new research methods and which report findings that have significant and clear implications for practitioners. The Journal publishes articles reporting research with a main focus on:

International Business and Management, Managerial issues in Business Context, New Challenges in Business, Methods and approaches in Management and Business, Strategic Management in business and management. Submissions should not only be methodologically sound, but also have significant innovative implications for researchers and practitioners. We also encourage researchers to submit original research papers concerning the ongoing issues in management and business. Since 2021 to new sections have been added to the journal as Short communications and Book Review.

Journal Policy

The European Journal of Studies in Management and Business publish open access articles under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) License which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited. The remaining journals offer a choice of licenses. All Research Councils UK (RCUK) and Wellcome Trust funded authors will be directed to the Creative Commons Attribution license (CC BY) by funder mandates effective on 1 April 2013.

Submission Guidelines

Article types

European Journal of Studies in Management and Business (Formerly Management and Business Research Quarterly) publishes articles reporting research in the field of management and business. The submissions should be about strategic management, marketing, management of marketing, customer and consumer satisfaction research, business management, human resource management, current approaches and challenges in management and business, and psychology in business and management. All articles are restricted to a maximum of 7000 words, including title, abstract, notes, references, tables, appendix, etc.

Peer review policy

European Journal of Studies in Management and Business (Formerly Management and Business Research Quarterly) has two-stage reviewing procedure. All articles are first reviewed by the editor-in-chief and editors to determine their suitability for external review. Articles accepted for external review are submitted to a strictly double-blind peer review. Each manuscript is reviewed by at least two external referees. All manuscripts are reviewed as rapidly as possible. Final editorial decision on acceptance, acceptance with minor revisions, or rejection is generally reached within 6-8 weeks after submission.

Plagiarism

European Journal of Studies in Management and Business (Formerly Management and Business Research Quarterly) takes issues of copyright infringement, plagiarism or other breaches of best practice in publication very seriously. We seek to protect the rights of our authors and we always investigate claims of plagiarism or misuse of published articles. Equally, we do aim to protect the reputation of the journal against malpractice. Submissions are checked with software. The major plagiarised submissions are desk rejected and the author is not allowed to submit any manuscript for three years. We also reserve the right to take up the matter with the dean or head of department of the author's institution and/or relevant academic bodies or societies.

Authorship

Papers should only be submitted for consideration once the authorization of all contributing authors has been gathered. No Change is made in contributing authors' order or name after submission.

How to submit your manuscript

European Journal of Studies in Management and Business adheres strictly to APA 7th Edition. The manuscript should not normally exceed 7000 words, including title, abstract, notes, references, tables, appendix, etc. Only electronic files conforming to the journal's guidelines will be accepted. The acceptable format for the text and tables of your manuscript is Word.doc. All manuscripts must be emailed to MBRQSubmissions@gmail.com or be submitted by [online submission](#). Please submit a cover letter confirming and mentioning:

The manuscript is not under review by another journal.

Manuscript title, authors, and name and mailing address of corresponding author

The manuscript has been formatted according to the conventions of APA 7th Edition

Please embed cover letter, title page, figures and tables in the manuscript to become one single file for submission (Word) in the journal website.

Article-processing charges

Open-access publishing is not without costs. European Journal of Studies in Management and Business (Formerly Management and Business Research Quarterly) therefore charges 160 EURO as Article Processing Charge for each article accepted for publication after a double-blind review. We routinely waive charges for authors from low-income countries. For other countries, article-processing charge waivers or discounts are granted on a case-by-case basis to authors with insufficient funds. Authors can apply for a waiver or discount during the submission process

Publication in Special Issues is free of charge for the accepted papers by the guest editors and reviewers

Contact

Any correspondence, queries or additional requests for information on the Manuscript Submission process should be sent to the Editorial Office as follows

Email: MBRQSUBMISSIONS@GMAIL.COM and MBRQEDITOR@EUROKD.COM

ABSTRACTING AND INDEXING:

[EBSCO Business Source Ultimate](#); [EBSCO Business Source Premier](#); [EBSCO Business Source Complete](#); [ECONBIZ](#); [ProQuest- Ulrich's Periodicals Directory](#); [Scilit](#); [Cabell](#); [EuroPub](#); [Sherpa Romeo](#); [COPERNICUS Master Journals List \(ICV 2022=100.00\)](#); [The European Reference Index for the Humanities and the Social Sciences \(ERIH PLUS\)](#); [Dimensions](#); [WorldCat](#); [MIAR](#); [J-Gate](#); [QUALIS 2017-2020: B3](#); [ISC](#); [ZDB](#); [EZB Electronic Journals Library](#); [Google Scholar](#); [ROAD](#); [Publons](#); [CrossRef](#);